

EFFECT OF IMPERFECTIONS ON THE VISCOELASTIC BUCKLING OF FIBER- REINFORCED PLASTIC LAMINATED PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The creep deflection of cross-ply laminates, having various magnitudes of imperfections, under in-plane compression is examined. The analysis is based on nonlinear viscoelastic approach. The stress function is obtained by solving the compatibility equation using the Laplace transform, and the deflection is calculated from the moment equilibrium equation by the Galerkin technique and a numerical integration scheme. The numerical results of deflection history for the Glass/Epoxy laminates are presented for illustrating the effect of imperfections on the buckling behavior. The solutions based on the quasi-elastic approach are also presented for comparison.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the plastic matrix of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) exhibits a viscoelastic behavior. While the elastic buckling of laminates has been investigated intensively, the creep buckling of FRP laminates attracts much less attention. Among a few works on this subject, Wilson and Vinson [1], and Kim and Hong [2] examined the buckling load reduction of laminated plates. Both works were conducted within the framework of the quasi-elastic analysis; i.e., the buckling load is obtained by direct substitution of time-varying properties into the elastic formulation of the problem. This approach is applicable for cases when the applied load is nearly timewise constant. However, in the process of buckling, the validity of constant loading assumption is questionable. The deflection is induced by the existence of the bending moment, which in turn depends mainly on the magnitude of the deflection. Therefore, the bending moment is time-varying, although the edge compression remains constant.

Another shortcoming in the above-mentioned works is that the analysis is based on the linear classical analysis without considering the effect of initial imperfections. It is known that the imperfection will affect the time at which the deflection grows rapidly [3]. In this study, the creep buckling of symmetric cross-ply FRP laminates, having various degrees of imperfections,

is examined based on the nonlinear viscoelastic analysis. The critical time is estimated from the deflection history. The viscoelastic results are compared with those results obtained using the quasi-elastic approach.

GOVERNING FORMULATIONS

Consider an FRP laminate as shown in Figure 1. The edge widths of the plate along the x and y directions are denoted as a and b , respectively; the thickness is h . The plate considered, having an initial deflection w_0 , sustains an in-plane compression force P along the x direction.

Figure 1. Laminated plate.

For the case of regular, symmetric cross-ply laminates, the stress resultants are related with strains and curvatures as

$$N_i = \sum_{j=1,2,6} A_{ij} \int_0^t (t-\tau) \frac{\partial \epsilon_j(x, y, \tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau = \sum_{j=1,2,6} A_{ij} * \epsilon'_j$$

$$M_i = \sum_{j=1,2,6} D_{ij} * \kappa'_j \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \tag{1}$$

where $A_{16} = A_{26} = D_{16} = D_{26} = 0$. The strains and curvatures in the above equations are

$$\epsilon_x = u_{,x} + (w_{,x})^2/2 + w_{,x}w_{0,x}$$

$$\epsilon_y = v_{,y} + (w_{,y})^2/2 + w_{,y}w_{0,y}$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = v_{,x} + u_{,y} + w_{,x}w_{,y} + w_{,x}w_{0,y} + w_{0,x}w_{,y}$$

$$\kappa_x = -w_{,xx} \quad , \quad \kappa_y = -w_{,yy} \quad , \quad \kappa_{xy} = -2w_{,xy} \tag{2}$$

where u , v and w are the middle plane displacements in the x , y and z directions.

Stiffnesses A_{ij} and D_{ij} listed in Eqns (1) are defined by

$$(A_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int (1, z^2) (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6)$$

in which $(\bar{Q}_{ij})_k$ are the transformed reduced stiffnesses of the k -th layer.

The in-plane gross equilibrium equations are

$$N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} = 0 \quad , \quad N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

The out-of-plane response is governed by

$$M_{x,xx} + 2M_{xy,xy} + M_{y,yy} + N_x(w + w_0)_{,xx} + 2N_{xy}(w + w_0)_{,xy} + N_y(w + w_0)_{,yy} = 0 \quad (4)$$

The stress function F which is defined by

$$N_x = F_{,yy} \quad , \quad N_y = F_{,xx} \quad , \quad N_{xy} = -F_{,xy} \quad (5)$$

reduces the equilibrium conditions to the form of

$$D_{11} * w'_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) * w'_{,xxyy} + D_{22} * w'_{,yyyy} - F_{,yy}(w + w_0)_{,xx} + 2F_{,xy}(w + w_0)_{,xy} - F_{,xx}(w + w_0)_{,yy} = 0 \quad (6)$$

The compatibility equation relating strains ϵ_i obtained from Eqns (2) is

$$\epsilon_{x,yy} + \epsilon_{y,xx} - \gamma_{xy,xy} = (w_{,xy})^2 - w_{,xx}w_{,yy} + 2w_{,xy}w_{0,xy} - w_{,xx}w_{0,yy} - w_{0,xx}w_{,yy} \quad (7)$$

By applying the Laplace transform to Eqns (1), (5) and (7), the compatibility equation can be expressed as

$$\hat{a}_{11} \hat{F}_{,xxxx} + (2\hat{a}_{12} + \hat{a}_{66}) \hat{F}_{,xxyy} + \hat{a}_{11} \hat{F}_{,yyyy} = s \mathcal{L}[(w_{,xy})^2 - w_{,xx}w_{,yy} + 2w_{,xy}w_{0,xy} - w_{,xx}w_{0,yy} - w_{0,xx}w_{,yy}] \quad (8)$$

where $[\hat{a}] = [\hat{A}]^{-1}$. Hereafter, a variable with a hat represents the Laplace transform of this variable.

VISCOELASTIC ANALYSIS

The creep deflections of simply-supported Glass/Epoxy laminates under in-plane compression are analyzed. The specific boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } x = 0, a : w = M_x = N_{xy} = 0, u = \text{constant and } \int_0^b N_x dy = -P \\ \text{at } y = 0, b : w = M_y = N_{xy} = 0, v = \text{constant and } \int_0^a N_y dx = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The deflections w_0 and w are expressed as

$$[w_0, w] = [A_0, A(t)] \sin(\alpha_m x) \sin(\beta_n y)$$

where $\alpha_m = m\pi/a$ and $\beta_n = n\pi/b$. The above deflection patterns satisfy the deflection and moment requirements at edges.

For the assumed deflection w and the prescribed imperfection w_0 , function \hat{F} can be determined from Eqn (8), and stress function F then obtained by performing the inversion is as follows,

$$F(t) = [\Phi_{11}/\lambda^2 \cos(2\beta_n y) + \Phi_{11}\lambda^2 \cos(2\alpha_m x)]*(A^2 + 2AA_0)' / 32 - Py^2 / (2b) \quad (10)$$

where

$$\lambda = \beta_n / \alpha_m, \quad \Phi_{11}(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}(1/\hat{a}_{11})$$

It is not difficult to show that the stress function F given above satisfies the in-plane boundary conditions listed in (9).

Substituting F into Eqn (6) and applying the Galerkin procedure yield the following nonlinear integro-differential equation :

$$-(P/P_{cr})D(0)(\bar{A}_0 + \bar{A}) + D*\bar{A}' + (\bar{A}_0^2 + \bar{A}_0\bar{A})(\Phi*\bar{A}')/8 + (\bar{A}_0 + \bar{A})[\Phi*(\bar{A}^2)']/16 = 0 \quad (11)$$

where parameters are

$$[\bar{A}, \bar{A}_0, \Phi] = [A, A_0, (1 + \lambda^4)\Phi_{11}]/h$$

$$D(t) = [D_{11} + 2\lambda^2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) + \lambda^4 D_{22}]/h^3, \quad P_{cr} = (\alpha_m)^2 b h^3 D(0)$$

The trapezoid integration rule is employed to obtain approximate solutions for the unknown deflection parameter \bar{A} from equation (11). Here, for the purpose of illustration, the numerical integration scheme for $D*\bar{A}'$ is presented as below.

Consider the value of $D * \bar{A}'$ from $t = 0$ to $t = t_j$ to be calculated. It is convenient to rewrite $D * \bar{A}'$ as follows,

$$D(t_j)\bar{A}(0) + \int_0^{t_j} D(t_j - \tau) d\bar{A}(\tau)$$

where t_k ($k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, j$) ($t_0 = 0$) are the time intervals. Applying the trapezoid rule to the above expression, the following numerical formulation can be obtained :

$$D(t_j)\bar{A}(t_0) + \sum_{k=0}^{j-1} \frac{1}{2} [D(t_j - t_k) + D(t_j - t_{k+1})] [\bar{A}(t_{k+1}) - \bar{A}(t_k)]$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Glass/Epoxy laminates considered are under an environment with temperature $T = 73^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity $M=96\%$. The creep compliances of FRP generally obey the following power law :

$$S_{11} = S_{11}(0) \quad , \quad S_{12} = S_{12}(0) \quad , \quad S_{22} = S_{22}(0)(1 + a_T(t/t_f)^b) \quad , \quad S_{66} = S_{66}(0)(1 + a_S(t/t_f)^b)$$

The material parameters of a unidirectional Glass/Epoxy lamina, measured at approximately 73°C and 21 % relative humidity, are [4] :

$$S_{11}(0) = 0.0267/\text{GPa} \quad , \quad S_{12}(0) = -0.00826/\text{GPa} \quad , \quad S_{22}(0) = 0.0942/\text{GPa}$$

$$S_{66}(0) = 0.233/\text{GPa} \quad , \quad a_T = 0.0846 \quad , \quad a_S = 0.151 \quad , \quad b = 0.27 \quad , \quad t_f = 1 \text{ hour}$$

For the viscoelastic laminae, the relations between relaxation moduli and creep compliances are in the form of Laplace transforms as

$$\sum_{j=1,2,6} s^2 \hat{Q}_{ij} \hat{S}_{jk} = \delta_{ik} \quad (i, k = 1, 2, 6)$$

The resulting relaxation moduli calculated from above equations are

$$Q_{11} = 1/S_{11}(0) + [Q_{11}(0) - 1/S_{11}(0)] \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\bar{a}_T)^k f_k(t)$$

$$[Q_{12} \quad , \quad Q_{22}] = [Q_{12}(0) \quad , \quad Q_{22}(0)] \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\bar{a}_T)^k f_k(t) \quad , \quad Q_{66} = Q_{66}(0) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (a_S)^k f_k(t)$$

where

$$\sum_{j=1,2,6} Q_{ij}(0) S_{jk}(0) = \delta_{ik} \quad (i, k = 1, 2, 6)$$

$$\bar{a}_T = S_{11}(0) Q_{11}(0) a_T \quad , \quad f_k(t) = [-\Gamma(b+1)]^k (t/t_f)^{kb} / \Gamma(kb+1)$$

The FRP material is assumed to be a simple material. The effect of the increase of moisture concentration on the creep behavior is accommodated in the constitutive equation by the use of "reduced time" [5]. If the variation of moisture is time-independent, the stress-strain relations for a lamina are

$$\sigma_i = \sum_{j=1,2,6} \int_0^t \bar{Q}_{ij}(t/a_c - \tau/a_c) \frac{\partial \epsilon_j(x, y, \tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (i = 1, 2, 6)$$

where the moisture shift factor a_c is related with the specific moisture content c as follows,

$$a_c = \exp(0.26 - 68.73c)$$

Meanwhile, the equilibrium moisture concentration c is related to the relative humidity M of the environment by the following law [6] :

$$c = 0.018(M/100)$$

The creep deflections of cross-ply Glass/Epoxy laminates, predicted based on the viscoelastic analysis and quasi-elastic approximation, are presented below. The laminates considered have various magnitudes of imperfections with $\lambda = 1$. The lay-up sequence of these regular, 8-layer laminates is $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_S$. Figures 2 and 3 show the deflection histories of laminates under compressive loadings $P/P_{cr} = 0.9$ and $P/P_{cr} = 0.8$, respectively.

Figure 2. Effect of imperfections on the creep deflections of cross-ply laminates : ($P/P_{cr} = 0.9$, $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_S$, $\lambda = 1$, $\bar{A} = A/h$, $\bar{A}_0 = A_0/h$).

Figure 3. Effect of imperfections on the creep deflections of cross-ply laminates : $(P/P_{cr} = 0.8, [(0^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_S, \lambda = 1, \bar{A} = A/h, \bar{A}_0 = A_0/h)$.

It is noted that the results based on both the viscoelastic and quasi-elastic analyses are close to each other when the laminates have a large imperfection (for example, $\bar{A}_0 = 0.01$). However, the deviations become larger for the cases of laminates having smaller imperfections. The quasi-elastic approach generally predicts a shorter loading duration without buckling. According to the quasi-elastic analysis, there is a finite critical time as the magnitude of the imperfection approaches zero. However, the more accurate viscoelastic analysis reveals that critical time depends strongly on the magnitude of the initial deflection. The critical time can be very large for a laminate having an extremely small imperfection. The effect of loading ratio P/P_{cr} on the deflection history is examined by comparing these two figures. For the case of $P/P_{cr} = 0.9$, the deflection grows rapidly around a certain time. But, for the case of a smaller compressive force $P/P_{cr} = 0.8$ the buckling phenomenon is not so obvious.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The nonlinear analysis of cross-ply Glass/Epoxy laminates with imperfections under in-plane compression has been conducted using the viscoelastic approach. The stress function is obtained analytically using the Laplace transform from the compatibility equation. Subsequently, the deflection parameter is calculated from the moment equilibrium equation by applying the Galerkin procedure and a numerical integration scheme. The results based on the quasi-elastic analysis are also obtained for comparison. The numerical results indicate that the quasi-elastic approach is applicable for the laminates having large imperfections. For the cases of small imperfections, the quasi-elastic approach predicts a finite critical time regardless of the magnitudes of imperfections, which is not true according to the viscoelastic analysis. In fact, the critical time depends strongly on the magnitudes of imperfections.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The support of this research by the National Science Council of Taiwan, R.O.C. through Grant NSC82-0401-E-019-18 is gratefully acknowledged.

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